

Effectiveness of Hibiscus Tea On Reduction of Blood Pressure Among Hypertensive Clients at Selected Community

Tamilselvi S¹

Professor,
Saveetha College of Nursing,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and
Technical Sciences,
Thandalam, Chennai.
tamildani@gmail.com

Thenmozhi P²

Professor,
Saveetha College of Nursing,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and
Technical Sciences, Thandalam,
Chennai.
thenmozhi.sethu@gmail.com

Mary Minolin T³

Professor,
Saveetha College of Nursing,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and
Technical Sciences,
Thandalam, Chennai
minolinbabu@gmail.com

Bhuvaneshwari G⁴

Professor,
Saveetha College of Nursing,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and
Technical Sciences,
Thandalam, Chennai.

bhuvana.prabha1981@gmail.com

Glishiya GV⁵

BSc Nursing,
Saveetha College of Nursing,
Saveetha Institute of Medical and
Technical Sciences,
Thandalam, Chennai.

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Abstract

Hypertension is a modifiable condition and a major risk factor for coronary heart disease, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease and chronic kidney disease. Hypertension poses a significant burden on public health, cardiovascular health and healthcare system in India. It is directly responsible for 57% of all stroke deaths and 24% of all coronary heart disease deaths in India.3 Important factors such as considerable and constant changes in work organization, structure and processes, excessive use of computers and smartphones, undue psychological stress due to high expectations and goals, materialism, lack of spiritual and social support, dietary habits, lack of physical activity, obesity, lack of sleep, impact the health of bankers employees .Objective The present study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of Hibiscus tea to reduce Blood pressure among Hypertensive clients in community setting. Method: The research design used for this study was quasi experimental, one experimental group and one control group. The non probability convenient sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. The total number of samples was 60 out of which 30 samples were experimental and 30 samples were control group. Data were collected by using a structured and

second part consists of a structured anxiety rating score. Results: The blood pressure of control pre-test, control post-test in the control group, the pretest mean was 130.33 and posttest mean was 123.40 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 18.68 and 14.07 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 130.33±18.68 and posttest was 123.40±14.07. The mean difference score was 6.93 and the value of 'T'= 1.7698 which is statistically not significant at P<0.05. in the experimental group, the pretest mean was 131.37 and posttest mean was 119.30 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 20.02 and 10.14 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 131.37±20.02 and posttest was 119.30±10.14. The mean difference score was 12.07 and the value of 'T'= 3.1058 which is statistically significant at P<0.05. Conclusion: There was a statistically significant association in the post test level of blood pressure among hypertensive patients in the experimental group than the control group. This indicates that the hibiscus tea is most effective non-pharmacological method and had no side effect which can be used to manage the level of blood pressure among hypertensive clients.

Keywords: Hibiscus tea, Hypertension, Hypertensive clients, Blood pressure.

Introduction

Hypertension is associated with 12.8% of all the deaths of the world. Many countries have implemented large -scale programs for hypertension and other chronic diseases, with various successes. Of the more than 1.3 billion people with hypertension worldwide, 82% live in low- and middle-income countries, and an estimated 220 million adults have hypertension in India alone. To address the challenge of noncommunicable diseases, India launched the National Programme for Prevention and Control of Cancer, Diabetes, Cardiovascular Diseases and Stroke (now known as the National Programme for Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases) in 2020. The National Health Mission for 100 districts in 21 states. However, few data are currently available to assess the success and potential for improvement of hypertension control at the subnational level. Approximately 1 billion adults worldwide suffered from hypertension in 2000, and this number is estimated to increase to 1.56 billion by 2025. The prevalence of hypertension is increasing rapidly in developing countries, where it is one of the leading causes of death and disability. Globally, 13% of premature deaths occur due to hypertension in developing and developed countries, and many African countries and some European countries currently have high average blood pressure (Miura K, et al., 2022). In Africa, hypertension (HTN) is one of the leading causes of heart failure. Globally, hypertension accounts for more than half of all stroke deaths.

Methods and Materials

A quantitative research approach was adopted for this study to accomplish the objectives of the study. The research design used for this study was quasi experimental, one experimental group and one control group. The dependent variable of the study is blood pressure among hypertensive clients. The independent variable of the study was picture based diversional activities. The target population of the study hypertensive clients. The total number of samples 60 out of which 30 samples were experimental and 30 samples were control group. Data collection was done in maduramangalam at, Chennai for a period of 1 week. The investigator obtained written permission from the authorities of selected community setting. Consent form was obtained from the hypertensive clients prior to the study. The purpose of the study was explained to the clients. The samples who fulfill the inclusion criteria were selected. The non probability convenient sampling technique was used to select 60 samples for the study. Demographic variable was collected. On the first day the blood pressure was measured by using sphygmomanometer and the intervention hibiscus tea was given. On the 7th day posttest was done to assess the blood pressure among hypertensive clients.

The data was collected and analyzed by using descriptive and infernal statistics.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

This deals with analysis and interpretation of the data collected from 60 (30- experimental group and 30-control group) hospitalized children. The data collected was organized, tabulated and analyzed according to the objectives.

RESULTS

Description of Demographic Variables of hypertensive clients Experimental and Control Group. In the experimental group most of people, 13(43.33%) in the experimental group belong to the age of 45-54 and 13(43.33%) in the control group belong to the age of 55-64, 21(70%) in the experimental group and 15(50%) in the control group are female, 16(53.33%) in the experimental group and 17(56.67%) in the control group follow non-vegetarian diet, 16(53.33%) in the experimental group and in the control group had some changes in their weight and 20(66.67%) in the experimental group had no bad habits and 10(33.33%) in the control group drinks alcohol.

Assessment of Pretest and Post Test Level of blood pressure among hypertensive clients in The Experimental and Control Group.

It shows that 8(26.67%) had normal level,

10(33%) had elevated level, 7(23.33%) had hypertension stage 1 and 5(16.67%) had hypertension stage 2 in pretest while in posttest, 13(43.33%) had normal level, 14(46.67%) had elevated level and 3(10%) had hypertension stage in the experimental group.

Percentage distribution of pretest and posttest levels blood pressure of in the experimental group. Frequency and percentage distribution of pretest and posttest level of blood pressure in the control group.

Level of Blood Pressure	Pre test		Post test	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	7	23.33	10	33.33
Elevated	9	30.00	13	43.33
Hypertension stage 1	8	26.67	6	20.00
Hypertension stage 2	6	20.00	1	3.33
Hypertension crisis	-	-	-	-

The table 5 shows that 7(23.33%) had normal level, 9(30%) had elevated level, 8(26.67%) had hypertension stage 1 and 6(20%) had hypertension stage 2 in pretest while in posttest, 10(33.33%) had normal level, 13(43.33%) had elevated level, 6(20%) had hypertension stage 1 and 1(3.33%) had hypertension stage 2 in the control group.

Percentage distribution of pretest and posttest levels blood pressure of in the control group

Comparison tables in Level of the blood pressure in the experimental group.

Level of blood pressure	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference Score	Paired 't' test & p-value
Pre test	131.37	20.02	12.07	t=3.1038 p=4.22E-03, Significant P<0.0, significant
Post test	119.30	10.14		

The table 6 shows that in the experimental group, the pretest mean was 131.37 and posttest mean was 119.30 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 20.02 and 10.14 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 131.37±20.02 and posttest was 119.30±10.14. The mean difference score was 12.07 and the value of 'T'= 3.1058 which is statistically significant at P<0.05. We can infer that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest levels of blood pressure.

Comparison tables in Level of the blood pressure in the control group.

Level of blood pressure	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference Score	Paired 't' test & p-value
Pre test	130.33	18.68	6.93	t=1.7698 p=0.0872 Not Significant
Post test	123.40	14.07		

The table 7 shows that in the control group, the pretest mean was 130.33 and posttest mean was 123.40 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 18.68 and 14.07 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 130.33±18.68 and posttest was 123.40±14.07. The mean difference score was 6.93 and the value of 'T'=

1.7698 which is statistically not significant at $P < 0.05$. We can infer that there is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest levels of blood pressure.

Association of posttest level of blood pressure among hypertensive clients with their selected demographic variables in the experimental group.

It shows that none of the demographic variables had shown statistically significant association with the posttest level of blood pressure among hypertensive clients in the experimental group.

Discussion

The overall findings support the effects of the hibiscus tea in hypertensive clients is minimizing the level of blood pressure indeed providing extra therapies will reduce the blood pressure among hypertensive clients and involving them with physical activities will help to do their daily activities peacefully and also improve and reduce their blood pressure level. In experimental group it shows that 8(26.67%) had normal level, 10(33%) had elevated level, 7(23.33%) had hypertension stage 1 and 5(16.67%) had hypertension stage 2 in pretest while in posttest, 13(43.33%) had normal level, 14(46.67%) had elevated level and 3(10%) had hypertension stage in the experimental group. In control group shows that 7(23.33%) had normal level, 9(30%) had elevated level, 8(26.67%) had hypertension stage 1 and 6(20%) had hypertension stage 2 in pretest while in posttest, 10(33.33%) had normal level, 13(43.33%) had elevated level, 6(20%) had hypertension stage 1 and 1(3.33%) had hypertension stage 2 in the control group. The pretest mean was 131.37 and posttest mean was 119.30 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 20.02 and 10.14 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 131.37 ± 20.02 and posttest was 119.30 ± 10.14 . The mean difference score was 12.07 and the value of 'T' = 3.1058 which is statistically significant at $P < 0.05$. We can infer that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest levels of blood pressure. The pretest mean was 130.33 and posttest mean was 123.40 while the standard deviation of pretest and posttest are 18.68 and 14.07 respectively. The mean score of pretest was 130.33 ± 18.68 and posttest was 123.40 ± 14.07 . The mean difference score was 6.93 and the value of 'T' = 1.7698 which is statistically not significant at $P < 0.05$. We can infer that there is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest levels of blood pressure.

Conclusion

There was a statistically significant association in the post test level of blood pressure among hypertensive patients in the experimental group than the control

group. This indicates that the hibiscus tea is most effective non-pharmacological method and had no side effect which can be used to manage the level of blood pressure among hypertensive clients.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of Interest

References

1. Forouzanfar MH, Liu P, Roth GA, Ng M, Biryukov S, Marczak L, et al. Global burden of hypertension and systolic blood pressure of at least 110 to 115 mm hg, 1990-2015. *JAMA* 2017;317:165-82.
2. Blood Pressure Lowering Treatment Trialists' Collaboration, Turnbull F, Neal B, Ninomiya T, Algert C, Arima H, et al. Effects of different regimens to lower blood pressure on major cardiovascular events in older and younger adults: Meta-analysis of randomised trials. *BMJ* 2008;336:1121-3.
3. Yoon SS, Carroll MD, Fryar CD. Hypertension prevalence and control among adults: United States, 2011-2014. *NCHS Data Brief* 2015;(220)1-8
4. Mills KT, Bundy JD, Kelly TN, Reed JE, Kearney PM, Reynolds K, et al. Global disparities of hypertension prevalence and control: A systematic analysis of population-based studies from 90 countries. *Circulation* 2016;134:441-50.
5. Esteghamati A, Meysamie A, Khalilzadeh O, Rashidi A, Haghazali M, Asgari F, et al. Third national surveillance of risk factors of non-communicable diseases (SuRFNCD-2007) in Iran: Methods and results on prevalence of diabetes, hypertension, obesity, central obesity, and dyslipidemia. *BMC Public Health*
6. Mittal BV, Singh AK. Hypertension in the developing world: Challenges and opportunities. *Am J Kidney Dis* 2010;55:590-8.
7. Whelton PK, He J, Muntner P. Prevalence, awareness, treatment and control of hypertension in North America, North Africa and Asia. *J Hum Hypertens* 2004;18:545-51
8. Brown MJ, Cruickshank JK, Dominiczak AF, MacGregor GA, Poulter NR, Russell GI, et al. Better blood pressure control: How to combine drugs. *J Hum Hypertens* 2003;17:81-6.
9. Wright JM, Musini VM, Salzwedel DM, Dormuth C. First-line diuretics versus other classes of antihypertensive drugs for hypertension. *Cochrane Database of Systematic*

Reviews 2009;4:5-9.

10. Muntner P, Carey RM, Gidding S, Jones DW, Taler SJ, Wright JT Jr., et al. Potential US population impact of the 2017 ACC/AHA high blood pressure guideline. *Circulation* 2018;137:109-18

11. Welz AN, Emberger-Klein A, Menrad K. Why people use herbal medicine: Insights from a focus-group study in Germany. *BMC Complement Altern Med* 2018;18:92.

12. Ernst E. Complementary/alternative medicine for hypertension: A mini-review. *Wien Med Wochenschr* 2005;155:386-91.

13. Haji Faraji M, Haji Tarkhani A. The effect of sour tea (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) on essential hypertension. *J Ethnopharmacol* 1999;65:231-6.

14. Herrera-Arellano A, Flores-Romero S, Chávez-Soto MA, Tortoriello J. Effectiveness and tolerability of a standardized extract from *Hibiscus sabdariffa* in patients with mild to moderate hypertension: A controlled and randomized clinical trial. *Phytomedicine* 2004;11:375-82.

15. Herrera-Arellano A, Miranda-Sánchez J, Avila-Castro P, Herrera-Alvarez S, Jiménez-Ferrer JE, Zamilpa A, et al. Clinical effects produced by a standardized herbal medicinal product of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* on patients with hypertension. A randomized, double-blind, lisinopril-controlled clinical trial. *Planta Med* 2007;73:6-12.

16. Hopkins AL, Lamm MG, Funk JL, Ritenbaugh C. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. in the treatment of hypertension and hyperlipidemia: A comprehensive review of animal and human studies. *Fitoterapia* 2013;85:84-94.

17. McKay DL, Chen CY, Saltzman E, Blumberg JB. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. Tea (tisane) lowers blood pressure in prehypertensive and mildly hypertensive adults. *J Nutr* 2010;140:298-303.

18. Mozaffari-Khosravi H, Jalali-Khanabadi BA, Afkhami-Ardekani M, Fatehi F, Noori-Shadkam M. The effects of sour tea (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) on hypertension in patients with type II diabetes. *J Hum Hypertens* 2009;23:48-54.

19. Negishi H, Xu JW, Ikeda K, Njelekela M, Nara Y, Yamori Y. Black and green tea polyphenols attenuate blood pressure increases in stroke-prone spontaneously hypertensive rats. *J Nutr* 2004;134:38-42.

20. Odigie IP, Ettarh RR, Adigun SA. Chronic administration of aqueous extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* attenuates hypertension and reverses cardiac hypertrophy in 2K-1C hypertensive rats. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2003;86:181

21. Sri Lekha, M. Vishnuram, Surya K, Ramana Abathsagayam, Kumaresan Suganthirababu, Prathap Efficacy of Dynamic Neuromuscular Stabilization Exercises on Balance and Fall Risk in Subjects with Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy among Geriatrics—A Pilot Study (2025) *Physical and Occupational Therapy in Geriatrics*, Cited 2 times. DOI: 10.1080/02703181.2025.2467803

22. Udhaya Kumar, Albert Anand Ramalingam, Vinodhkumar Moussallem, Charbel D.Gopal, Kumaraguruparan Biomechanical impact of foot pronation on anterior knee pain – case controlled study (2025) *Fizicna Reabilitacia ta Rekreativno-Ozdorovci Tehnologii*, 10 (1), pp. 35 - 41, Cited 0 times. DOI: 10.15391/prrht.2025-10(1).05

23. Dhanusia, S.; Shareen, Akbar A.; Suganthirababu, Prathap Srinivasan, Vignesh ; Kumar, Priyadharshini ; Jayaraj, Vanitha; Vishnuraman, Suriya ; Umasankar, Yamini Murugaiyan, Poovarasan Effectiveness of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy and Aerobic Exercise in Parkinson Disease Dementia: A Pilot Study (2025) *Physical Treatments*, 15 (2), pp. 165 - 174, Cited 0 times. DOI: 10.32598/ptj.15.2.663